

1 **Novel transcriptional functions and interaction partners for the Sirtuin family.**

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7 The Sirtuin family is described to possess functions in aging and lifespan. We measured total transcription
8 by RNA-sequencing in human umbilical vein cells containing engineered, forced expression of SIRT6 to
9 discover novel transcriptional targets of the Sirtuin family. Sirtuin 6 activated *NFKB2* and *MAFB*. Induction
10 of SIRT6 resulted in activation of *CCRL2*. Sirtuin 6 activated *IL17RE* but repressed *TNFSF18*. Solute
11 carrier transporter *SLC7A14* was silenced by SIRT6 providing context for study of SIRT6. SIRT6
12 expression in human cells resulted in complete silencing of *BDNF*.

13 Citations

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16 homeostasis via Hif1 α . *Cell*, 140(2), pp.280-293.

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